

Parental support for the Academic Recovery Programme

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For the Organisation of Eastern Caribbean States

<https://opendeved.net>

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1. Stay in touch with your child's instructor(s)

This can be done through WhatsApp, SMS, phone calls, emails, even in writing. It is important to **provide feedback** on your child's learning at home experiences and seek counsel where necessary.

2. Connect with other parents with children in the same class as yours

This is an opportunity to **ask questions, learn about new resources, seek advice, and tackle issues together.**

3. Create a routine for your child

Create a **balanced routine** that includes breakfast, online classes, lunch breaks, bathroom breaks, play time, homework time ect. This enables you to **monitor your child and ensure that they are completing tasks** on time.

4. Make sure assignments are submitted on time

Ensure that your child does their assignments and **submits them on time**. You may **supervise** them while doing the assignments and help them if need be. You should also consider having a **dedicated time** for assignments. **You must not write in your children's books or do assignments for them.**

5. Cater to your child's emotional wellbeing

Provide reassurance when your child is struggling and **use positive terminology to speak to your child**. For example, encourage them to retry tasks they have skipped because of difficulties, and praise them for their efforts - remind them that, even if they have not yet reached the answer, they are doing well. Remember to also take some 'me time' for yourself.

6. Model/demonstrate difficult concepts

To model something is to **demonstrate** how it is done. For example, you can model how to solve a mathematical problem or how to break down a word to pronounce it. It involves **showing** the child how to do it **step by step** and asking them to demonstrate it while you provide feedback.

7. Seek feedback from and partnership with the teacher

Create a short **video clip** of your child doing some homework or classwork - or of you working with your child - and send it to the teacher for **feedback**. Build a **strong relationship** with your child's teacher so that you can better support your child's learning at home.

8. Listen to your child and their teacher

This involves taking time to **listen** to your **child's** and their **teacher's feedback** in a way that ensures that you have not just heard, but understood clearly what they mean. One way to do this is to **ask clarifying questions** or repeat what they said in your own words. For example, you can say, "From what you just said, I am understanding that... is this what you meant?"

9. Ask for help

Ask for help when your child is struggling. **Reach out to the teacher**, describe the problem and ask for steps that you can take.

10. Make use of all resources

Make use of **online resources, professionals** in the community and relatives and friends who have **knowledge** to provide extra **guidance** and training where you need it. (See also the last slide of this presentation.)

Thank you

Further online resources for parents

- <https://readingmate.co.uk/app/>
- <https://www.khanacademy.org/>
- <https://www.readworks.org/>
- <https://www.ereadingworksheets.com/>

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Acknowledgements

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